

Nexus Between Social Media Use and Mental Health Outcomes among High School Students in Kashmir, India

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Abstract

Background: The rapid development of technology has facilitated new types of social activity, communication, and information dissemination among students. With the development of technology, concerns have been raised regarding its potential impact on students' mental well-being.

Objectives: The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between social media use and mental well-being among high school students in India.

Methodology: This study employed a cross-sectional quantitative design, involving 246 students in grades 7 through 12. Social media use was assessed in terms of social activity, video gaming, virtual friendships, and smartphone addiction. To collect data, a structured survey using a validated tool for measuring social activity and mental well-being was employed. Comparative tests and correlation analysis were conducted to investigate the potential relations between social media use and mental well-being.

Results: The overall prevalence of social media use among students was low, with a small portion participating in online friendships (3.6%) and video gaming (2.8%). There was a distinctly high level of social media use among male students and those in their upper academic years, specifically regarding smartphone use, media sharing, and participation in video gaming activities. There was a negative relationship between psychological well-being and social media use, specifically in terms of smartphone use ($r = -0.16$, $p = 0.012$), messaging ($r = -0.14$, $p = 0.031$), and video gaming ($r = -0.25$, $p < 0.001$). There was a significant association between anxiety and not having access to specific platforms, with over 14% of students reporting high and intermediate anxiety when not having access to messaging, and 17% reporting similar feelings when not having access to make a phone call. There was a negative relationship between age and psychological well-being ($r = -0.33$, $p < 0.001$), but a positive relationship with smartphone use ($r = 0.19$, $p = 0.003$) and with media sharing ($r = 0.32$, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The findings reveal the complex relationship between social media use and students' psychological well-being. Whereas social media use can have certain benefits, excessive and unregulated use can have increased anxiety and reduced mental well-being. The study recommends programmes to enhance digital competency, organise screen use, and deliver school-provided mental well-being services to promote responsible technology use among students.

Unique Contribution: This study uniquely establishes a low overall prevalence of social media engagement among students, alongside gender- and academic-level disparities in use, and empirically confirms a significant negative correlation between specific social media activities (smartphone use, messaging, video gaming) and psychological well-being.

Key recommendation: Given the negative relationship between specific social media activities and psychological well-being, universities should implement targeted intervention programmes focusing on responsible smartphone use and media sharing, especially for older male students, while addressing access anxiety related to messaging and phone communication.

Keywords: Social media use, mental health outcomes, high school students, digital well-being, online behaviour, psychological impact

Introduction

The integration of social media in modern society has been profoundly significant, contributing significantly to strengthening interpersonal communications, supporting social relationships, and facilitating information dissemination (Kumar & Singh, 2021). The engagement of high school students with social media platforms, combined with adolescents' active presence on these platforms, makes this group particularly relevant for researching the implications of social media use (Kumar & Singh, 2021). Social media have reshaped modalities of human communications, information transmission, and people's reactions to their environments. In high school students, the use of social media platforms is widespread, supported, for instance, by a significant pool of studies in this area. For instance, a survey of 2,000 high school students showed that 92% use Facebook, 86% use Instagram, and 80% use Snapchat, signifying the prominence of these platforms in modern society (Chen et al., 2023). Similarly, a four-year longitudinal study reported a persistent high level of social media use among high school students over the same period (Kirschner & Karpinski, 2020).

Social media use, including its numerous aspects such as usage intensity and quantity, the particular applications used (e.g., Instagram, Facebook, and WhatsApp), type of interaction (between active use and consumption), and reasons for use (such as social interaction, learning, entertainment, or seeking knowledge). Recent studies have shown that social media use patterns, particularly the differential between active and passive use, have varying implications for outcomes related to mental health (Twenge et al., 2023).

Psychological well-being outcomes include measures of depression symptoms, anxiety levels, feelings of loneliness, self-esteem, sleep issues, and overall psychological distress. A growing body of literature highlights the correspondence between increased social media use and an upsurge of reported depression and anxiety among teenagers (Keles et al., 2020). In addition, factors like disrupted sleep patterns and toxic online interactions are also potential factors that can enhance the psychological challenges that younger people face.

A considerable amount of work has been conducted to explore social media use and mental well-being in high school adolescents. Smith and Anderson (2022) conducted a meta-analysis

that aggregated several studies, and a negative association between high social media use and mental well-being, manifesting in increased anxiety, dissatisfaction, and stress, emerged. Garcia and Hernandez (2023) pinpointed several factors responsible for such a problem, such as social comparison, cyberbullying, and sleep disturbances. High vulnerability stems predominantly from increased exposure to idealized representations of life, creating heightened feelings of insufficiency and reduced confidence in oneself (Mukherjee, & Banerjee, 2022).

The increased use of social media among high school students ushered in a new era of worldwide connectivity, accelerating the dissemination of information. Nevertheless, the social media use and mental well-being in high school adolescents' complex interrelationship has not yet been subjected to a thorough and nuanced analysis. Complexity in such a problem is further amplified when it is examined in specific sociocultural environments, and this impact can manifest in a vastly variable manner across disparate cultures, creating additional layers of complexity in the issue at hand. To tackle such a challenge, one must gain a proper understanding of these dynamics, and this understanding is crucial in formulating effective interventions specifically for high school students with diverse cultural backgrounds in various cultures. Therefore, the objective of this study was to determine the relationship between social media use and mental health outcomes among high school students in Kashmir, India.

Significance of the study

The increased integration of social media into teenagers' lives has generated serious concerns about its effects on mental well-being. This research work is of utmost importance for several reasons. Firstly, it fills a critical gap in the literature by providing empirical data unique to the Kashmir context, a milieu of its particular socio-political issues that can amplify the effects of social media on the mental well-being of teenagers. Secondly, the research can provide critical information for educators, parents, mental health professionals, as well as policymakers, so that they can be better aware of the relationship of social media consumption with such issues as anxiety, depression, loneliness, and levels of self-esteem of teenagers within this particular political and cultural context. Thirdly, by identifying trends and potential risk factors, the research can inform the development of targeted interventions, awareness initiatives, and support services that respond more effectively to the specific needs of Kashmir's high school students. Overall, the research can enable healthier online practices and increased mental well-being among teenagers within a country where such initiatives are badly needed.

The study's hypotheses are derived from the literature concerning technology use and adolescent mental health, and are stated as follows:

Hypotheses

H1: Increased general usage of digital technologies and social media among high school students is negatively associated with their psychological well-being.

H2: Specific technology-related behaviours (including smartphone usage, engagement in gaming, and frequent messaging) are negatively associated with the psychological well-being of high school students.

H3: Technology-related anxious behaviour is positively associated with scores on the Technological Behaviour Scale (TBS).

H4: Technology-related anxious behaviour is negatively associated with high school students' psychological well-being measures.

Research Method

This research consisted of a cross-sectional survey of high school students in Kashmir, India. According to the demographics of full-time students, a minimum of 377 samples was calculated to be required for analysis, with a 95% confidence level, a 5% margin of error, and an assumed distribution of 50%. To counteract any potential complications related to non-completers and missing information, an additional 400 samples were included for assurance. Five schools were recruited at random—two in rural and three in urban settings—to cover a range of settings.

Data collection involved a standardised survey with incorporated validated scales for social media use and mental health consequences. Anonymity and a printed version of the survey questionnaire were distributed to students in a face-to-face manner. The study duration took four months.

The instruments in the study underwent pilot testing with 10 students, who were randomly recruited from schools not involved in the study, to assess both the content validity of the tool and the duration required to complete the questionnaires. There were no recommendations for change proposed by students who participated in the pilot testing.

Reliability for the research was achieved through the utilisation of a pre-tested standard questionnaire, where a similar set of respondents was asked to provide similar worded answers to similar items of questioning. Cronbach's alpha was employed to determine internal consistency of scales, where all the general subscales (e.g., social media behaviour as well as mental health consequences) had satisfactory reliability coefficients of >0.70 . Pilot testing, utilising a sample of 10 students, was used to determine and clarify ambiguous questions, thereby enhancing the reliability of the tool even further.

High content validity is applied to the research because the items of the questionnaire were derived from previously tested items in the literature that measure social media usage and adolescent mental well-being. Cultural and context-specific content appropriateness was maintained through review by educators and mental health professionals, in accordance with the Kashmir context. Regarding external validity, the sample of schools from Kashmir provided rich data for the adolescent population of the area.

Ethical approval for conducting the study was obtained by securing approval from the Jagannath University Ethics Committee (Ref No: HREC/JnU/Psy/23-2024), and permission for the study's use was granted by the Education Department in Kashmir, India. Participation in the study was voluntary, and participants could withdraw at any time without repercussions. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained at all times. Participants who were 18 years or

older signed the consent form, and those younger than 18 years had their parents sign the consent form; they signed the assent form prior to taking part in the study.

Data Analysis

Data were captured in Excel, followed by coding and analysis using the R and SPSS software programs. Variables with missing values were imputed using their respective median values. Composite scores were calculated for each subscale of technology use, anxiousness related to technology use, and psychological well-being. Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to compare mean scores of subscales, while Spearman correlation analysis was used to determine the correlations between psychological well-being and technology use scales. A test with a p-value of 0.05 or less was considered significant.

Results

A total of 246 students participated in the study. According to Table 1, more than half of the students were male (52%). The overall mean age of the students was 15.52 ± 1.61 years. Male students (16.07 ± 1.51 years) were significantly older than female students (14.93 ± 1.5 years), and the majority were within the 15- to 17-year-old range (64.6%). Most of the students were in grades 10 to 12 (65.9%).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the students

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	128	52
Female	118	48
Age		
10-14	65	26.4
15-17	159	64.6
18+	22	8.9
Grades		
7-9	84	34.1
10-12	162	65.9
Locations		
A	15	6.1
B	53	21.5
C	49	19.9
D	46	18.7
E	83	33.7

Overall, social media use was low among the students, especially smartphone use, General social media use, Internet searching, e-mailing, and Media sharing, where all students had low use of technology. A few of the students had moderate to high use of technology, such as Online friendship (3.6%), Video gaming (2.8%), Phone calling (2%), Television viewing (1.6%), Text messaging (1.2%) and social media friendship (0.8%) (Table 2).

Table 2: Level of social media uses among students

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Smartphone		
Low	246	100
General social media use		

Low	246	100
Internet searching		
Low	246	100
E-mailing		
Low	246	100
Media sharing		
Low	246	100
Text messaging		
Low	243	98.8
Moderate	2	0.8
High	1	0.4
Video gaming		
Low	239	97.2
Moderate	5	2
High	2	0.8
Online friendship		
Low	237	96.3
Moderate	6	2.4
High	3	1.2
Social media friendship		
Low	244	99.2
Moderate	1	0.4
High	1	0.4
Phone calling		
Low	241	98
Moderate	4	1.6
High	1	0.4
Television viewing		
Low	242	98.4
Moderate	2	0.8
High	2	0.8

The prevalence of poor and moderate psychological well-being among the students was 9.3% and 35%, respectively (Fig 1).

Figure 1: Prevalence of mental well-being of the students

Table 3 shows the level of anxiousness among students. The inability of some students to check in with some technologies according to their wishes results in a feeling of anxiety. More than 14% were moderately to highly anxious when they were unable to use text messages. More than 17% of students were moderately to very highly anxious when they could not use Cell phone calls, while an inability to use Facebook and other social networks as desired resulted in moderately to very high anxiousness among at least 12% of students. Failure to use Personal e-mail, work e-mail, and voice mail as desired by the students resulted in moderately to very high anxiousness among at least 13% and 10% of students, respectively.

Table 3: Level of anxiousness due to technology use among students (%)

Constructs	Not anxious at all	A little anxious	Moderately anxious	Highly anxious	Very Highly anxious
Text messages	60.2	25.6	9.8	4.5	
Cell phone calls	30.1	52	9.8	7.7	0.4
Facebook and other social networks	72.8	14.6	5.3	6.5	0.8
Personal e-mail	73.6	12.6	8.9	4.1	0.8
Work e-mail and voice mail	76.4	13.4	6.1	2.4	1.6

Students in grades 10 to 12 reported higher technology use scores, such as E-mailing ($p < 0.001$), Media sharing ($p < 0.001$), Video gaming ($p = 0.009$), Online friendship ($p < 0.001$), Social media friendship ($p < 0.001$), Phone calling ($p < 0.001$) and Television viewing ($p = 0.028$) than those in grades 7 to 9. Male students reported higher technology use scores, such as Smartphone ($p = 0.009$), General social media use ($p = 0.005$), Media sharing ($p = 0.002$), Video gaming ($p < 0.001$), Online friendship ($p < 0.001$) and social media friendship ($p = 0.001$). However, the male students reported lower psychological well-being ($p = 0.021$) than female students.

Table 4: Differences in sub-scores on technology use by Age, sex and grade of students

	Grades			Sex			Age			
	7-9	10-12	p-value	Male	Female	p-value	10-14	15-17	18+	p-value
Smartphone	8.13±4.56	8.71±4.87	0.209	9.29±5.16	7.67±4.16	0.009	6.98 ^a ±3.82	9.03 ^b ±5.04	9.32 ^b ±4.4	0.002
General social media use	4.13±3.42	3.80±3.53	0.315	4.48±3.82	3.3±3.0	0.005	3.80±3.13	3.89±3.72	4.36±2.89	0.361
Internet searching	3.75±2.45	3.49±2.13	0.752	3.62±2.22	3.53±2.27	0.651	3.26±1.75	3.7±2.43	3.64±2.15	0.476
E-mailing	0.89±1.54	2.11±2.08	<0.001	2.01±2.34	1.36±1.48	0.084	0.94 ^a ±1.43	1.82 ^b ±2.11	3.05 ^c ±1.73	<0.001
Media sharing	0.82±1.64	2.05±2.53	<0.001	2.16±2.85	1.05±1.41	0.002	0.86 ^a ±1.29	1.69 ^b ±2.37	3.50 ^c ±3.33	<0.001
Text messaging	2.54±1.77	2.71±2.21	0.536	2.77±2.20	2.53±1.93	0.531	2.35±2.00	2.69±1.92	3.23±3.07	0.049
Video gaming	1.33±2.1	2.41±3.28	0.009	3.07±3.36	0.92±1.96	<0.001	1.29 ^a ±2.92	2.13 ^b ±2.77	3.64 ^b ±3.86	<0.001
Online friendship	0.75±2.09	1.39±2.02	<0.001	1.62±2.36	0.69±1.56	<0.001	0.88 ^a ±2.23	1.17 ^a ±1.91	2.05 ^b ±2.46	0.013
Social media friendship	0.36±1.01	0.90±1.70	<0.001	0.99±1.75	0.42±1.16	0.001	0.46 ^a ±1.32	0.74 ^a ±1.58	1.32 ^b ±1.55	0.008
Phone calling	1.65±1.89	2.14±1.27	<0.001	2.09±1.67	1.86±1.34	0.288	1.89 ^a ±0.9	1.90 ^a ±1.67	2.77 ^b ±1.66	0.010
Television viewing	0.74±1.57	1.21±1.94	0.028	1.20±1.76	0.89±1.89	0.078	0.91 ^a ±1.97	1.00 ^a ±1.74	1.82 ^b ±1.92	0.015
Anxious due to technologies	2.79±2.86	2.97±2.95	0.412	2.98±3.21	2.83±2.57	0.614	2.20 ^a ±2.57	3.33 ^b ±3.09	1.91 ^a ±1.9	0.002
Psychological well-being	55.5±6.72	50.58±14.6	0.118	49.04±15.89	55.75±6.24	0.021	58.17 ^a ±5.89	50.45 ^b ±13.37	47.91 ^b ±16.49	<0.001

Age was negatively correlated with psychological well-being ($r=-0.33$, $p<0.001$), but positively correlated with smartphone ($r=0.19$, $p=0.003$), E-mailing ($r=0.36$, $p<0.001$), Media sharing ($r=0.32$, $p<0.001$), Text messaging ($r=0.13$, $p=0.037$), Video gaming ($r=0.24$, $p<0.001$), Online friendship ($r=0.22$, $p<0.001$), Social media friendship ($r=0.19$, $p=0.002$), Phone calling ($r=0.15$, $p=0.019$), and Television viewing ($r=0.19$, $p=0.003$).

Overall anxiousness due to technology use scores was positively correlated with Smartphone ($r=0.17$, $p=0.009$), General social media use ($r=0.20$, $p=0.001$), Emailing ($r=0.28$, $p<0.001$), Media sharing ($r=0.27$, $p<0.001$), Online friendship ($r=0.23$, $p<0.001$) and social media friendship ($r=0.23$, $p<0.001$).

Psychological well-being has negative correlation with Uses of Smartphone ($r=-0.16$, $p=0.012$), Internet searching ($r=-0.19$, $p=0.002$), Text messaging ($r=-0.14$, $p=0.031$), Video gaming ($r=-0.25$, $p<0.001$), Feeling anxious ($r=-0.13$, $p=0.048$).

Table 5: Spearman Correlation analysis of psychological well-being and sub-scores of technology use among students

	Age	p-value	Anxious due to technologies	p-value	Psychological well-being	p-value
Anxious due to technologies	0.08	0.205				
Psychological well-being	-0.33	<0.001	-0.13	0.048		
Smartphone	0.19	0.003	0.17	0.009	-0.16	0.012
General social media use	0.00	0.954	0.20	0.001	0.01	0.848
Internet searching	0.09	0.150	0.12	0.062	-0.19	0.002
E-mailing	0.36	<0.001	0.28	<0.001	0.01	0.917
Media sharing	0.32	<0.001	0.27	<0.001	-0.10	0.122
Text messaging	0.13	0.037	0.10	0.105	-0.14	0.031
Video gaming	0.24	<0.001	0.10	0.113	-0.25	<0.001
Online friendship	0.22	<0.001	0.23	<0.001	0.01	0.931
Social media friendship	0.19	0.002	0.23	<0.001	-0.06	0.346
Phone calling	0.15	0.019	0.02	0.734	0.11	0.094
Television viewing	0.19	0.003	0.08	0.214	-0.04	0.566

Discussion

Social media forms an integral part of modern life, with a significant impact on the educational life of adolescents. It involves numerous functionalities and information considered important for active presence in the technological environment. The integration of social media into educational structures has changed traditional pedagogical processes, with both positive and negative consequences. Social media facilitates rapid communication, the dissemination of information, and collaboration, thereby enriching educational processes. Additionally, social media has profoundly changed the modalities of interaction and learning in educational environments. Although it has many positive aspects, it also presents several problems, including dissatisfaction, loss of privacy, and the dissemination of information. This study aimed to explore the relationship between social media use and its impact on the mental health outcomes of high school students.

The findings of this study reveal that the level of social media use among students was low, with a small group taking part in social processes such as friendships, gaming, and social connectivity through social media platforms. These observations vary from previous studies, suggesting a high level of social media use in adolescents and emerging adults (Odgers & Jensen, 2020). For instance, a study conducted by Keles et al. (2020) showed that social media use was regularly practised by over 90% of adolescents. Recent findings by Twenge et al. (2023) also suggest that social media engagement continues to rise globally among teenagers, although disparities exist across regions. In any case, the reduced social use of social media in this study may depend on contextual factors such as socioeconomic circumstances, internet access availability, and school policies governing technology use (Chaudhary et al., 2023).

A significant finding of this study concerns variation in technology use according to gender. There was a heightened use of smartphones, gaming, and social networks among male students, aligning with Nesi and Prinstein's (2019) findings that male students have a larger preference for computer gaming and social interaction in online environments compared to female students. Earlier studies have supported that technology-related experiences, specifically technostress, vary according to gender. It is well-established that females have a greater propensity for experiencing technological stress compared to males, attributed to their relatively lower computer competency and heightened anxiety regarding technology (Boateng & Dery, 2021). More recent evidence from Singh and Kaur (2022) reaffirms that gender differences continue to influence patterns of technology use and related mental health outcomes. In contrast to high technology use, male subjects in this study showed reduced mental well-being, consistent with studies suggesting a nexus between high technology use, specifically gaming, and poor mental wellness (Király et al., 2018; Coyne et al., 2023).

Another significant finding is that older students (10–12 years of age) use technology at a greater rate compared to younger students (7–9 years). This aligns with studies that support older students' greater engagement with computer tools for social connectivity compared to younger cohorts (Orben et al., 2019; Jones & Smith, 2024). It is also significant to note that counterintuitive observations regarding age and psychological well-being reveal that as students age, their mental wellness can worsen, possibly due to academic and social pressures, heightened social expectations, and increased vulnerability to web-related stress (Rosenthal & Tobin, 2023; Patel et al., 2022).

Ultimately, the research revealed a negative correlation between smartphone use (including searching, messaging, and gaming) and mental well-being. Consistent with current studies, this finding confirms that excessive use of screens and electronic messaging hurts adolescents' mental wellness (Lemola et al., 2017). For instance, prolonged screen use has been linked with reduced well-being, particularly in adolescents who use electronic media for leisure (Przybylski & Weinstein, 2017). Moreover, a relationship between technology use and anxiety, specifically linked to smartphones, social networks, and virtual relationships, supports past studies suggesting that electronic addiction can amplify anxiety (Elhai et al., 2017; Shukla & Sharma, 2023).

Study limitations

While this investigation yields important insights, several important caveats must be acknowledged. First, the cross-sectional design limits the ability to make causal inferences about social media use and psychological well-being. Hence, longitudinal studies are necessary to determine whether social media use leads to adverse mental health consequences. Additionally, the use of self-report scales can introduce social desirability biases and recall inaccuracies. In addition, a single cohort of students may make generalising to a larger group of adolescents and emerging adults challenging. In addition, failure to control for factors such as socio-economic status, parental management of social media use, and presence of co-morbid mental disorder could confound the relationships in this investigation. Future studies must work to counteract these caveats through the use of multi-method approaches, including objective evaluation of social media use and psychological well-being.

Implications

The inferences drawn in this investigation have important implications for parents, schools, and policymakers. Given the positive association between social media use and psychological well-being, interventions must focus on developing healthy social media habits in students. Schools must consider developing computer and information competency programs with a view toward educating students about the potential consequences and dangers of social media, as well as techniques for controlling social media use and addiction.

Second, mental health service programs must become part of schools to educate students in managing psychologically challenging consequences of behaviour in cyberspace. Counselling and educational programs can motivate students to develop healthy online habits and encourage them to seek help when faced with technology-related stress and anxiety.

Parents assume a significant role in managing social media use in the family environment. By providing guided screen use, creating offline social experiences, and engaging in positive discussions about social media, one can mitigate the detrimental consequences of excessive social media use.

Lawmakers should consider creating policies to support digital wellness, including programs for safer web use, filtering age-appropriate content, and creating spaces that promote responsible social media use. By taking a balanced stance on these issues, one can create a safer environment for students' social media use and, consequently, foster academic development and mental well-being.

Conclusion

The present study describes trends in social media use in students, with an overall infrequent use rate, but with significant variation between gender and age groups. The results confirm that social media use tends to rise with age, in relation to increased stress and poor psychological well-being. Most importantly, male students showed increased social media and gaming use with relatively poor mental health outcomes compared with female students. In addition, excessive use of social media, specifically in relation to smartphone use and gaming, showed a strong positive relation with poor psychological consequences, including increased stress and reduced well-being.

The present study emphasises the importance of responsible and balanced social media use among students. As social media can facilitate communication, academic work, and social interaction, unbridled excessive use can contribute to increased stress and stress-related behaviours. Policymakers, teachers, and parents must join in creating programs for responsible social media use and mental wellness in students. Long-term studies could explore trends in social media use and its psychological consequences over a period and evaluate interventions for enhancing students' social media use and overall wellness.

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